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The Power of Music

Music is universal. As society has evolved and changed, music has stuck around and continuously evolved alongside it. Having been around for more than 35,000 years, it has made significant impacts on modern day society and people. Whether it be the beat, instruments, or lyrics— music consists of several different and intrinsic parts that make it purposeful to each individual. To many, music is something they listen to for simple enjoyment, but to others, it is a place where they can truly express themselves and their creative side. For people like my friend, Louie Sabio, music has been heavily integrated in his life from a young age and is now a place where he can “turn to and find comfort during tough times” (Sabio).

Being in rigorous music programs, playing instruments, and talking to musical relatives all initially drew Louie to music. Though it was all new, fresh, and tough at times, he has always been a natural star and loved learning more. Additionally, having grown up in the Bay Area, its unique and “hyphy” music and culture has significantly impacted the ways in which he approaches and creates his own music today. With his first debut song, “Do This” feat. Haile, Louie remembers “just having fun” when writing the song and “not expecting much out of it” (Sabio). The effects were greater. After the release of this song, I remember attending several parties and social events where the second someone played “*Do This*,” everyone would go crazy. People would gather, and crowds of teenagers would slowly come in, dancing to the beat of his song. It was in an instant that everyone would drop whatever it was they were doing and

automatically levitate towards the crowd, singing word-for-word with all their enthusiasm. Louie's charisma and natural talent drew in a large crowd of supporters whose faces would brighten with excitement as his music would play. In these moments when different people would come together in support of him, we subsequently would all form one big, diverse, and beautiful community.

Some may think of music as something that just plays in the background, but they fail to acknowledge the greater impacts it has on individuals and communities. It is more than "just music," as it allows people to form deeper connections and relate to one another. Louie remembers being in high school and always having his conversations with people go straight to music. There were never any awkward interactions, as the second there would be an ounce of silence, the conversation would pick right up to anything along the lines of music: did you hear about Kanye? Have you listened to Drake's new song? Any new music? Whether it be the daily rap news or what he currently is working on, the topic of music would always find its way into conversations, allowing for him to meet new people and form new friendships/relationships upon these common interests.

Listening to music is one thing, but creating and producing it is a whole other. The process consists of many complex steps which involve hours of thinking and working. However, for naturals like Louie these steps come easier, as he sees the process of creating music as a place where he can have expressive and creative freedom, and less as a job. Music should not be forced and ideas should flow easily from your head to paper. The vast steps including finding a beat, making melodies, and piecing lyrics together, "should take you through a roller coaster of emotions" (Sabio). Louie mentions how the style of music he decides to create is heavily

impacted by his mood in that current moment. He says, “If I’m in a good mood, I’m going to put out something that gets people dancing or head nodding” (Sabio).

As I spoke more to Louie during our interview, I noticed that as he expressed the ways in which music makes him feel, his face would brighten and his smile would widen. It was like in that moment, all he could think back to were those moments in which music empowered and bettered him. He even said that one of his favorite things about music is, “being able to go back to a certain memory because it’s very nostalgic” (Sabio). Music serves several purposes, but being able to associate certain songs to certain memories is truly special as it has the power to make us feel, whether it be good, bad, or anything in between. Louie’s past experiences drew him to the music world, and it is because of music and the freedom he feels with it, that he is the person he is today.

Though the creativity process should flow relatively smoothly, it is not uncommon to go completely blank and struggle every now and then. Similar to an author’s “writer’s block,” music artists often find themselves struggling to even get one lyric that they like. Louie recalls several instances where he has produced music just to simply not like the song in the end. It is hard to pinpoint what exactly is “wrong,” but rather than giving up on it, Louie goes back and works even harder as he has always pushed to only produce the best. He claims his perfectionism to be one of his toxic traits, as it often holds him back from releasing what could potentially be a hit! However, “having people who can give him positive critiques” and “not be a yes-man” is Louie’s ideal person to work with (Sabio). He acknowledges how collaborating with others is one of the most important aspects of music, and how he has been able to use and apply this trait for the real world. He also highlights how he produces his best music when he is collaborating with others because they “encourage creativity” (Sabio). The skills that are learned in music, such as

collaboration and creativity, go way further than just in the music world, it can also be applied to important real world situations and interactions.

Music can do so much for a person who really, truly wants it. Through all of Louie's hardships growing up, he always found comfort and amusement with music. Unknowing of all the opportunities that can arise with music, he continued to pursue music through tough times because it remained a deep passion of his. Today, it has opened so many doors for him as he is now a music major at New York University with several opportunities to work with other top tier students in order to produce what he loves. Though the ultimate goal of his, like anyone else, is to find a job, Louie mainly hopes to remain happy and not get too caught up in worrying about a job because, "at the end of the day happiness is what truly matters" (Sabio).

Because creating, listening, and producing music all make Louie feel as though he is on top of the world, he mainly hopes to "keep the cycle going" by "trying to reciprocate that same positive energy back" in his own music (Sabio). With all the heart and soul that is put into creating a song, it is not surprising the impact it has on people. The beauty of creating music is being able to make others feel some sort of emotion through your own words. The messages that are sent and received through songs create larger impacts that affect people's daily lives and actions. As a creator, Louie hopes to send the message that music serves more than just one purpose and is so multi-dimensional that we can approach it in whatever manner we want or need.

Works Cited

Sabio, Louie. Personal Interview. 16 October. 2021.